

Vibration analysis and control using Macro Fiber Composites (MFC)

Joshit Mohanty^{1*} Sanjay H. Upadhyay²

^{1*}*Veer Surendra Sai University of Technology, Sambalpur*

²*Indian Institute of Technology, Roorkee*

¹joshit.mohanty@gmail.com

²upadhyaysanjayh@yahoo.com

Abstract

Inflatable Structures are gaining immense importance in space science. The idea of large, ultra-lightweight and compactable membrane space structures has been proposed for various future interplanetary space missions. The performance efficiency of these reflective surfaces depends not only on the geometric accuracy of these surfaces but also on their vibration characteristics. It means the surface of the space structures (antenna reflector, telescope mirror, solar sail etc.) must be error free. So, to get high accuracy surface requirements of the space structures, the measurement and analysis of reflector's accuracy are necessary. Also, due to the periodic nature of symmetric reflectors, they will be very sensitive to even small irregularities due to manufacturing and material tolerances. Such irregularities can affect the vibration behavior significantly, by localizing the vibration modes and confining the energy to a region close to the source. The vibration challenges while launching by launch vehicle's high frequency and small vibration due to the electronics component of the satellite on orbit.

This paper considers a control system for vibration control of space membrane structures with piezoelectric actuators. Optimization and control techniques are discussed. Fuzzy Logic Control system is taken into account. Macro Fiber Composites (MFCs) are being used as PZT stack actuators. A robust comparison is shown between the PID controller and Fuzzy controller. A non-contact monitoring and control system has been proposed which has scope in future on complete development.

1. Introduction

1.1 Overview

Gossamer space structures are considered viable among proposed large space structures that will make innovative missions possible such as space habitats and satellite antenna reflectors. These structures are comprised of thin membrane and highly flexible support structures. When compared with the conventional space structures, the advantages of gossamer space structures are ultra-lightweight, small volume packages, and large unfolded area. The lightweight design makes the gossamer space structure have some special dynamic properties, such as very low stiffness, low damping ratios, and low modal

frequencies. Due to these properties, the gossamer space structures are extremely susceptible to vibration and the vibration energies are hard to disperse in the space. Vibration problem makes the surface of the gossamer space structure distortion and questions its stability. In the high-precision application area, such as membrane antenna and membrane optic reflectors, vibration control of the gossamer space structure is ultra-needed. Vibration control of gossamer space structure is an extremely challenging problem. The more effective way is to use active vibration control technology. Active vibration control of gossamer space structure has been ongoing since 2000. Three research points are focused by most researchers: the system dynamic modeling, the actuator, and the control methodology.

1.2 Inflatable Structures

Inflatable space structures are structures which use pressurized air/ other chemicals to maintain shape and rigidity. These structures are extremely light weight and expand after their launch, thus allowing to pack big packages into a small volume. However, these are prone to vibrations occurring during launching of space craft and other dynamic vibrations occurring after they are activated. The cause of vibrations includes structural, thermal and signal transmission (space particles hitting the reflectors).

Gossamer Space Structure

In engineering, we use the term gossamer structure to mean the general category of space ultra-low mass structures, such as inflatable or many other forms of expendables. A space – inflatable structure is a specific application of a membrane structure or any ultra-low mass hybrid structure with an extensive use of membranes. We mean by membrane those structures (load carrying artifacts or devices) comprised of highly flexible (compliant) plate or shell-like elements. This usually implies thin, low modulus materials, such as polymer films. Membrane structures have very little inherent bending stiffness, nor do they lend themselves well to carrying compressive loads. Thus, they are usually tensioned – planar or inflated-curved configuration.

Fig. 2 i. Human habitats, ii. Space antenna Reflectors iii. Space Antenna
 (Pictures: i. NASA ii. Kerbal Space Program iii. University of Strathclyde)
 iii. Deployable Waveguide Antenna using membrane (Pictures: L Garde Smart Space Technologies)

2. Structure Materials

2.1 Kapton

Fig. 3 Kapton sheets

Kapton is a polyimide film developed by DuPont in the late 1960s that remains stable across a wide range of temperatures, from -269 to $+400$ °C (-452 to 752 °F; 4 – 673 K). Kapton is used in, among other things, flexible printed circuits (flexible electronics) and thermal blankets used on spacecraft, satellites, and various space instruments.

The chemical name for Kapton K and HN is poly (4,4'-oxy diphenylene-pomalidomide). It is produced from the condensation pyromellitic dianhydride and 4,4'-oxydiphenylamine. Kapton synthesis is an example of the use of a dianhydride in step polymerization. The intermediate polymer, known as a "polyamic acid)", is soluble because of strong hydrogen bonds to the polar solvents usually employed in the reaction. The ring closure is carried out at high temperatures (200 – 300 °C, 473 – 573 K).

2.2 Kevlar

Kevlar is the registered trademark for a para-aramid synthetic fiber, related to other aramids such as Nomex and Technora. Developed by Stephanie Kwolek at DuPont in 1965, this high-strength material was first commercially used in the early 1970s as a replacement for steel in racing tires. Typically, it is spun into ropes or fabric sheets that can be used as such or as an ingredient in composite material components.

Currently, Kevlar has many applications, ranging from bicycle tires and racing sails to body armor, because of its high tensile strength-to-weight ratio; by this measure it is 5 times stronger than steel. It is also used to

make modern drumheads that withstand high impact. When used as a woven material, it is suitable for mooring lines and other underwater applications.

2.3 Actuator Materials

2.3.1 Polyvinylidene fluoride, or polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF)

Fig. 5 (Polyvinylidene fluoride, or polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF))

It is a highly non-reactive thermoplastic fluoropolymer produced by the polymerization of vinylidene difluoride. PVDF is a specialty plastic used in applications requiring the highest purity, as well as resistance to solvents, acids and bases. Compared to other fluoro polymers, like polytetrafluoroethylene (Teflon), PVDF has a low density (1.78 g/cm^3). It is available as piping products, sheet, tubing, films, plate and an insulator for premium wire. It can be injected, molded or welded and is commonly used in the chemical, semiconductor, medical and defense industries, as well as in lithium-ion batteries. It is also available as a cross linked closed-cell foam. used increasingly in aviation and aerospace applications.

The piezoelectric properties of PVDF are exploited in the manufacture of tactile sensor arrays, inexpensive strain gauges, and lightweight audio transducers. Piezoelectric panels made of PVDF are used on the Venetia Burney Student Dust Counter, a scientific instrument of the New Horizons space probe that measures dust density in the outer solar system.

2.3.2 Macro Fiber Composites (MFCs)

The **Macro Fiber Composite (MFC) is the leading low-profile actuator and sensor** offering high performance, flexibility and reliability in a cost competitive device. The MFC was invented by NASA in 1996. Smart Material started commercializing the MFC as the licensed manufacturer and distributor of the patented invention worldwide in 2002. Since then, the MFC has been continuously improved and customized to fit the customers' specific needs and to meet the requirements for new applications.

Fig. 7 MFC Films acts as actuators

Advantages:

- a. Flexible, durable and reliable;
- b. Increased strain actuator efficiency;
- c. Directional actuation and sensing;
- d. Damage tolerant;
- e. Available as elongator (d33 mode) and contractor (d31 mode);
- f. Conforms to surfaces;
- g. Readily embeddable;
- h. Environmentally sealed package;
- i. Demonstrated performance;
- j. Different piezo ceramic materials available;
- k. Available also in **single crystal** PMN-PT,

Properties	PVDF Films	Macro Fibre Composites
1. Tensile Modulus	56 MPa	30.336 GPa
2. Modulus	Flexural – 2 GPa	Shear – 5.15 GPa
3. Optimum Working Zone	90°C-100°C	<120°C
4. Operating Temperature	<160°C	<130°C
5. Failure Temperature	177°C	150°C
6. Operating Frequency	10GHz	Sensor-1MHz , Actuator-700KHz

3. Optimization Techniques

In the simplest case, an optimization problem consists of maximizing or minimizing a real function by systematically choosing input values from within an allowed set and computing the value of the function. The generalization of optimization theory and techniques to other formulations comprises a large area of applied mathematics. More generally, optimization includes finding "best available" values of some objective function given a defined domain (or input), including a variety of different types of objective functions and different types of domains.

Besides (finitely terminating) algorithms and (convergent) iterative methods, there are heuristics. A heuristic is any algorithm which is not guaranteed (mathematically) to find the solution, but which is nevertheless useful in certain practical situations. List of some well-known heuristics:

- a. Memetic Algorithm;
- b. Differential Evolution;
- c. Evolutionary Algorithms;
- d. Dynamic Relaxation;
- e. Genetic Algorithms;
- f. Hill Climbing;
- g. Nelder – Mead Simplicial Heuristic;
- h. Particle Swarm Optimisation;
- i. Gravitational Search Algorithm;
- j. Artificial Bee Colony Optimization;
- k. Simulated Annealing;
- l. Stochastic Tunneling;
- m. Tabu Search;
- n. Reactive Search Optimization;

3.1 Genetic Algorithm

Genetic Algorithm (GA) is based on natural selection of species as proposed by Darwin. In nature, from a given population the fittest or the one who adapts to the surrounding are transferred to the next generation. Similarly in computational analysis, from a set of points, the adaptive ones are selected for next iteration. It goes over a cycle till the maximum possible fittest solution is obtained or maximum number of iterative solutions have been done. The simplest form of genetic algorithm involves three types of operators: selection, crossover (single point), and mutation.

- i. **Selection:** This operator selects chromosomes in the population for reproduction. The fitter the chromosome, the more times it is likely to be selected to reproduce.
- ii. **Crossover:** This operator randomly chooses a locus and exchanges the subsequences before and after that locus between two chromosomes to create two offspring. For example, the strings 10000100 and 11111111 could be crossed over after the third locus in each to produce the two offspring 10011111 and 11100100. The crossover operator roughly mimics biological recombination between two single-chromosome (haploid) organisms.
- iii. **Mutation:** This operator randomly flips some of the bits in a chromosome. For example, the string 00000100 might be mutated in its second position to yield 01000100. Mutation can occur at each bit position in a string with some probability, usually very small (e.g., 0.001).

Steps in Genetic Algorithm

The GA is used to determine the optimum placement of actuators to damp the vibrations. The positions are evaluated based on modal analysis of the membrane structure. Approx. 20% area is only available for their positioning.

4. Control Engineering & Methodologies

Mathematical optimization is used in much modern controller design. High-level controllers such as model predictive control (MPC) or real-time optimization (RTO) employ mathematical optimization. These algorithms run online and repeatedly determine values for decision variables, such as choke openings in a process plant, by iteratively solving a mathematical optimization problem including constraints and a model of the system to be controlled.

Fig. 8 An overview of control network in a random system

Various kinds of control methodologies can be used to control the vibrations of the gossamer space structure, such as:

- i. Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) Control,
- ii. Negative Feedback Control,
- iii. Robust Control,
- iv. Neural Control Network,
- v. Fuzzy Control, and,
- vi. Decentralized Control.

Fuzzy Control method, as one of the most popular methodologies, has the following advantages:

1. Do not require the mathematical model of the plant;
2. Can easily deal with system uncertainty and non-linearities;
3. Allows integrate control schemas.

4.1 PID Control System

A proportional – integral – derivative controller (PID controller) is a control loop feedback mechanism (controller) commonly used in industrial control systems. A PID controller continuously calculates an error value as the difference between a desired set point and a measured process variable and applies a correction based on proportional, integral and derivative terms (sometimes denoted as P,I and D respectively) which give their name to the controller type. For discrete systems, the PSD (proportional-summation-difference) is used.

where K_p , K_i , K_d are all non negative terms and denote the coefficients for proportional, integral and derivative terms.

Fig. 9 A sample fig showing working of PID controller

4.2 Fuzzy Control System

Fuzzy controllers are very simple conceptually. They consist of an input stage, a processing stage, and an output stage. The input stage maps sensor or other inputs, such as switches, thumbwheels, and so on, to the appropriate membership functions and truth values. The processing stage invokes each appropriate rule and generates a result for each, then combines the results of the rules. Finally, the output stage converts the combined result back into a specific control output value.

The most common shape of membership functions is triangular, although trapezoidal and bell curves are also used, but the shape is generally less important than the number of curves and their placement. From three to seven curves are generally appropriate to cover the required range of an input value, or the "universe of discourse" in fuzzy jargon.

As discussed earlier, the processing stage is based on a collection of logic rules in the form of IF-THEN statements, where the IF part is called the "antecedent" and the THEN part is called the "consequent". Typical fuzzy control systems have dozens of rules.

5. Mathematical Modeling & Description

5.1 Piezoelectric Stack Model

The piezoelectric stack consists of numerous thin layers of lead zirconate titanate (PZT) ceramic laminated together and electrically connected in parallel. The length of the piezoelectric stack actuator is l_a and the height of the piezoelectric stack actuator and the support frame are h_a and $2h$, respectively. The actuator is modeled as a super element with three nodes (i, j, k). The super element contains a spring element, a beam element, and a piezoelectric element. Assume all the piezoelectric patches of the piezoelectric stack have the exact same physical parameters.

Fig. 9: Piezoelectric stack actuator model (a) Force analysis

of the actuator (b) Finite element model of the actuator
(c) Electric connection of the piezoelectric stack.

Define u_i , u_j , and u_k as the displacement of the nodes i , j , and k . Then, $\overline{\delta_{pzl}} = [u_j \quad u_k]^T$ is the element displacement of the piezoelectric element. Assume the deformation of the piezoelectric stack is homogeneous. Then, the shape function of the piezoelectric element can be defined as

$$\mathbf{N}_{pzl} = \left[1 - \frac{x}{l_{pzl}} \quad \frac{x}{l_{pzl}} \right] \quad (1)$$

where l_{pzl} is the length of the piezoelectric stack. Then, the strain matrix of the piezoelectric element is

$$\mathbf{B}_{pzl} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathbf{N}_{pzl} = \left[\frac{-1}{l_{pzl}} \quad \frac{1}{l_{pzl}} \right] \quad (2)$$

The displacement and strain in the position x can be expressed as

$$u_{pzl}(x) = \mathbf{N}_{pzl} \overline{\delta_{pzl}} \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_3(x) = \mathbf{B}_{pzl} \overline{\delta_{pzl}} \quad (4)$$

As shown in Figure 9 (c), the electric field strength in the piezoelectric stack is

$$E_3 = -\frac{n_{pzl}\varphi}{l_{pzl}} \quad (5)$$

where φ is the applied voltage and n_{pzl} is the number of the piezoelectric patches. According to the equation of the piezoelectric, the stress in the piezoelectric stack is

$$\sigma_3 = \frac{\varepsilon_3}{s_{33}^E} - \frac{d_{33}E_3}{s_{33}^E} = \frac{\mathbf{B}_{pzl} \overline{\delta_{pzl}}}{s_{33}^E} + \frac{d_{33}n_{pzl}\varphi}{s_{33}^E l_{pzl}} \quad (6)$$

where d_{33} and s_{33}^E are the piezoelectric–mechanical coupling constant and the compliance constant, respectively. Then, the electric displacement in the piezoelectric is

$$D_3 = d_{33}\sigma_3 + \chi_{33}^{\sigma} E_3 = \frac{d_{33} \mathbf{B}_{pzl} \overline{\delta_{pzl}}}{s_{33}^E} + \frac{(d_{33})^2 n_{pzl} \varphi}{s_{33}^E l_{pzl}} - \frac{n_{pzl} \chi_{33}^{\sigma} \varphi}{l_{pzl}} \quad (7)$$

where χ_{33}^{σ} is the dielectric constant. The kinetic energy and potential energy of the piezoelectric stack can be expressed as

$$T_{pzl} = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \rho_{pzl} \dot{u}_{pzl} \dot{u}_{pzl} dV = \frac{1}{2} \int_{l_{pzl}} \rho_{pzl} A_{pzl} \dot{\delta}_{pzl}^T \mathbf{N}_{pzl}^T \mathbf{N}_{pzl} \dot{\delta}_{pzl} dz \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} U_{pzl} &= \frac{1}{2} \int_V (\varepsilon_3 \sigma_3 - E_3 D_3) dV \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_V \left[\frac{\overline{\delta}_{pzl}^T \mathbf{B}_{pzl}^T \mathbf{B}_{pzl} \overline{\delta}_{pzl}}{s_{33}^E} + \frac{2 \mathbf{B}_{pzl} \overline{\delta}_{pzl} d_{33} n_{pzl} \varphi}{s_{33}^E l_{pzl}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \left(\chi_{33}^{\sigma} - \frac{d_{33}^2}{s_{33}^E} \right) \frac{n_{pzl}^2 \varphi^2}{l_{pzl}^2} \right] dV \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where ρ_{pzl} and A_{pzl} are the density and cross-sectional area of the piezoelectric stack. Let $[u_k, u_j, Q_\varphi]$ and $[F_k, F_j, Q_\varphi]$ be the generalized coordinate and generalized force, respectively; where $Q_\varphi = -\chi_{33}^{\sigma} n_{pzl} \varphi / l_{pzl}$ is the applied charge. According to the Lagrange equation

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{u}_i} \right) - \frac{\partial T}{\partial u_i} + \frac{\partial U}{\partial u_i} = F_i \quad (10)$$

The dynamic equation of the piezoelectric stack can be written as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{M}}_{uu} \ddot{\boldsymbol{\delta}}_{pzt} + \tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{uu} \boldsymbol{\delta}_{pzt} + \tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{u\varphi} \varphi = \tilde{\mathbf{F}} \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{u\varphi}^T \boldsymbol{\delta} + \tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{\varphi\varphi} \varphi = Q_\varphi \quad (12)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{F}} = [F_k, F_j]$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{M}}_{uu}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{uu}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{u\varphi}$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{\varphi\varphi}$ are the mass matrix, elastic stiffness matrix, piezoelectric coupling matrix, and dielectric stiffness matrix, respectively.

$$\tilde{\mathbf{M}}_{uu} = \int_0^{l_{pzt}} \rho_{pzt} A_{pzt} \mathbf{N}_{pzt}^T \mathbf{N}_{pzt} dz = m_{pzt} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{uu} = \int_0^{l_{pzt}} \frac{A_{pzt}}{s_{33}^E} \mathbf{B}_{pzt}^T \mathbf{B}_{pzt} dz = k_{pzt} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{u\varphi} = \int_0^{l_{pzt}} \frac{B_{pzt} d_{33} n_{pzt} A_{pzt}}{s_{33}^E l_{pzt}} dz = k_{u\varphi} \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{\varphi\varphi} = \int_0^{l_{pzt}} \left(-\chi_{33}^\sigma + \frac{d_{33}^2}{s_{33}^E} \right) \frac{n_{pzt}^2 A_{pzt}}{l_{pzt}} dz = k_{\varphi\varphi} \quad (16)$$

where $m_{pzt} = \rho_{pzt} A_{pzt} / l_{pzt}$, $k_{pzt} = A_{pzt} / s_{33}^E$, $k_{u\varphi} = n_{pzt} d_{33} A_{pzt} / s_{33}^E$, and $k_{\varphi\varphi} = ((d_{33}^2 / s_{33}^E) - \chi_{33}^\sigma) (n_{pzt}^2 A_{pzt} / l_{pzt})$. By assembling the element mass matrix and stiffness matrix together, the dynamic equations of the actuator are as follows

$$\mathbf{M}_{uu}^e \ddot{\boldsymbol{\delta}}^e + \mathbf{K}_{uu}^e \boldsymbol{\delta}^e + \mathbf{K}_{u\varphi}^e \varphi^e = \mathbf{F}^e \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{u\varphi}^e T \boldsymbol{\delta}^e + \mathbf{K}_{\varphi\varphi}^e \varphi^e = Q_\varphi^e \quad (18)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\delta}^e$ and \mathbf{F}^e are the displacement vector and force vector, respectively, and φ^e and Q_φ^e are the voltage and applied charge, respectively. \mathbf{M}_{uu}^e , \mathbf{K}_{uu}^e , $\mathbf{K}_{u\varphi}^e$, and $\mathbf{K}_{\varphi\varphi}^e$ are the mass matrix, elastic stiffness matrix, piezoelectric coupling matrix, and dielectric stiffness matrix of the actuator, respectively.

5.2 Equation of motion

By using finite element method, the dynamic equation of the smart gossamer space structure can be written as

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\boldsymbol{\delta}} + \mathbf{G} \dot{\boldsymbol{\delta}} + \mathbf{K} \boldsymbol{\delta} + \mathbf{K}_{u\varphi} \varphi = \mathbf{F}_q \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{\varphi u} \boldsymbol{\delta} + \mathbf{K}_{\varphi\varphi} \varphi = Q \quad (20)$$

Where \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{G} , and \mathbf{K} are the mass, damping, and stiffness matrix, respectively; $\mathbf{K}_{u\varphi}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{\varphi\varphi}$ are the piezoelectric–mechanical coupling matrix and dielectric stiffness matrix, respectively; $\mathbf{K}_{\varphi u} = \mathbf{K}_{u\varphi}^T$; $\boldsymbol{\delta}$, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\delta}}$ and $\ddot{\boldsymbol{\delta}}$ are the displacement, velocity, and acceleration vectors of the finite element assemblage; \mathbf{F}_q is the mechanical force; and φ is the control voltage. The damping matrix is calculated by Rayleigh damping model as follows

$$\mathbf{G} = \alpha\mathbf{M} + \beta\mathbf{K} \quad (21)$$

where α and β are the constant factors. According to equation (20), we can obtain

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi} = \mathbf{K}_{\varphi\varphi}^{-1}(\mathbf{Q} - \mathbf{K}_{\varphi u}\boldsymbol{\delta}) \quad (22)$$

Substituting equation (22) into (19), we can obtain

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\boldsymbol{\delta}} + \mathbf{C}\dot{\boldsymbol{\delta}} + \bar{\mathbf{K}}\boldsymbol{\delta} = \mathbf{F}_q + \mathbf{U}\boldsymbol{\varphi} \quad (23)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{K}} = \mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_{u\varphi}\mathbf{K}_{\varphi\varphi}^{-1}\mathbf{K}_{\varphi u}$ and $\mathbf{U} = -(\mathbf{x}^s_{33} \mathbf{n}_{pzt}/\mathbf{l}_{pzt}) \mathbf{K}_{u\varphi} \mathbf{K}_{\varphi\varphi}^{-1}$. The mode, natural frequency, and damping ratio of the dynamic system are $\Phi = [\Phi_1, \Phi_2, \dots, \Phi_N]$, $\omega = \text{diag}(\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_N)$, and $\zeta = \text{diag}(\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \dots, \zeta_N)$, respectively. Then, the dynamic equation can be translated to mode coordinate

$$\ddot{\boldsymbol{\eta}} + 2\xi\omega\dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}} + \omega^2\boldsymbol{\eta} = \mathbf{F}_{qm} + \mathbf{U}_m\boldsymbol{\varphi} \quad (24)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\eta} = [\eta_1, \eta_2, \dots, \eta_N]^T$, $\mathbf{F}_{qm} = \mathbf{F}^T\mathbf{F}_q$, and $\mathbf{U}_m = \Phi^T\mathbf{U}$.

5.3 State-space model

For control synthesis, the system must be drawn up as first-order ordinary differential equation. Introduce a state vector

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \eta_i \\ \dot{\eta}_i \end{bmatrix} (i = 1, \dots, n) \quad (25)$$

Assuming that the control system uses accelerate signal as system output, the output equation is as follows

$$\mathbf{y}_i = \mathbf{C}_{am}(i)\ddot{\eta}_i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{C}_{am}(i) \end{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{x}} \quad (26)$$

Then, the dynamic equation can be written into decentralized state space form

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_i = \mathbf{A}_i\mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{B}_i\varphi_i + \mathbf{W}_i \quad (27)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_i = \mathbf{C}_i\mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{D}_i\varphi_i + \mathbf{V}_i \quad (28)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}_i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -\omega_i^2 & -2\xi_i\omega_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \mathbf{U}_m(i) \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ \mathbf{C}_{am}(i) & -2\mathbf{C}_{am}(i)\xi_i\omega_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

$$\mathbf{D}_i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \mathbf{C}_{am}(i)\mathbf{U}_m(i) \end{bmatrix} \quad (32)$$

$$\mathbf{W}_i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \mathbf{F}_{qm}(i) \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

$$\mathbf{V}_i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \mathbf{C}_{am}(i)\mathbf{F}_{qm}(i) \end{bmatrix} \quad (34)$$

5.4 Fuzzy controller

In order to simplify the controller design process, a standard fuzzy controller is designed for the bending and torsion control channels. The standard fuzzy controller receives the acceleration signal e (S_b or S_t) and its derivative ec (\dot{S}_b or \dot{S}_t) as input and gives the control voltage u (U_b or U_t) as output. The fuzzy domain of the input (E and EC) and output (U) variables belongs to $[-10, 10]$. Hence, we use constant coefficient k_E , k_{EC} , and k_U to scale the value

$$k_E = \frac{\max(|E|)}{\max(|e|)}$$

$$k_{EC} = \frac{\max(|EC|)}{\max(|ec|)}$$

$$k_U = \frac{\max(|U|)}{\max(|u|)}$$

Seven fuzzy sets (NL, NM, NS, ZO, PS, PM, and PL), two input power sets (E and EC), and one output power set (U) are employed in this report. The labels NL, NM, NS, ZO, PS, PM, and PL refer to the linguistic values: negative large, negative medium, negative small, zero, positive small, positive medium, and positive large, respectively. The sigmoidal membership functions and symmetric Gaussian membership functions

are used for input power set. The triangular membership functions are used for output power set. In this report, 49 AND-type rules are used to describe the present FC system. All rules have weights equal to 1. These rules are presented in Table 1.

		EC						
		NL	NM	NS	ZO	PS	PM	PL
E	NL	NL	NL	NL	NL	NM	ZO	ZO
	NM	NL	NL	NL	NM	NM	ZO	ZO
	NS	NM	NM	NM	NS	ZO	PS	PS
	ZO	NM	NM	NS	ZO	PS	PM	PM
	PS	NS	NS	ZO	PS	PM	PM	PM
	PM	ZO	ZO	PM	PM	PL	PL	PL
	PL	ZO	ZO	PM	PL	PL	PL	PL

6. Modelling & Software Analysis

Fig. 9 Fuzzy Inference System

Fig. 10 Membership function plots of the (a) input and (b) output power set.

Fig. 11 Simulink Model of the control system using Fuzzy Logic of Single Input Single Output (SIMO)

The fuzzy logic controller system is first designed keeping in mind the practical set up. The fuzzy inference is at first build up and then called in the model. Plant is designed which consists of the sensors, actuators and membrane set up. The random signal (vibration) is given to the fuzzy inference system which feeds the processed signal to the plant and the error in the next cycle in the next cycle is processed again. The cycle continues until a desired damping of the unwanted vibrations is achieved.

2. Results and Discussion

a. PID Controller

The control network and results of fuzzy logic controller are discussed above. In this section, a robust comparison of fuzzy logic and PID controller is made. The Simulink model of PID controller is presented below.

Fig. 16 Simulink model of PID controller

Fig. 12 A sample signal damping of membrane structure using PID controller

b. Fuzzy Logic Controller

The FIS (Fuzzy Inference System) is designed with 7 * 7 parameters as discussed above. The value are categorized from negative big to positive big. The inference is drawn according to the input signal and output voltage is obtained. The variation of surface of such an inference system is given in fig. 12.

Fig. 13 Fuzzy inference system output surface.

Fig. 14 E vs V graph (surface)

Fig. 15 EC vs V graph (surface)

Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 shows the variation of one input signal E and EC with output voltage V, respectively.

Fig. 16 A sample signal damping of membrane structure using fuzzy logic controller

The damping of the input random vibration signal is plotted in fig. 15, showing the system gets damped or becomes stable up to 90% in just 10 cycles in fuzzy logic network when compared with PID controller network.

3. Conclusion

This report addressed the active vibration control of inflatable structures. First, the dynamic modeling of the structure system is built. Fuzzy logic control system is proposed for control network. MFCs with large bending strengths are more effective in damping vibrations while PVDF are useful for high frequency vibrations. Piezoelectric stack actuator having large output force is very suitable for gossamer space structures which have a flexible frame. Finally, comparison is done on control characteristics between fuzzy logic controller and PID controller.

The advanced section of this research focuses on non-contact basis vibration analysis and control using EMWs.

The proposed system

A EMW "A" is transmitted from the transmitter which will be used to know the vibration and its characteristics – frequency and amplitude after it reflects from the surface. When "B" EM wave hits the surface of the reflector it adds some noise due to the vibrations of the membrane "V". After it passes the membrane, we get "B"+"V" at the rear side of the membrane. At this point we get a complicated wave of "A"+"B"+"V" = "C". A negative feedback from the upper surface is given to this point, which will help in getting "A" from "C". Now, the information from "A" will determine "V". Hence, finally will get "B". Now, as "A" is all over the surface, it really helps to determine the regions where we need to damp the vibrations. Say "B" is pure form of wave(or maximum obtainable wave) from the outer space, and at regions we are getting "B"+"N" (N- Noise). Lets say "V1" is the vibrations of the region where the obtained "B" is unaffected, than "V1"-N" is the additional required energy that is needed to damp the additional vibrations in that region. So in this region, firing "A"+"(V1"-N") wave will help in damping the disturbed vibrations.

There may be instances, where the required energy to damp the vibrations is more than the threshold energy of the surface. In that case, targeting the direct beam of energy might be harmful for the structure. Here we need to use less energy beams to counter those vibrations.

Ex: If the required energy is that of a blue beam of light and that is more than the threshold energy of the surface, we will tune the system for green light (that has considerably lower energy than the threshold

energy). The system will take “t1” seconds more to get stable, but all the vibrations will get damp. The “t1” additional seconds corresponds to

1. Number of photons that will reflect after hitting the surface;
2. Number of photons will not resonance with the surface vibration energy in order to transfer their energy to damp those vibrations.

PZTs/MFC Patches	Continuous PZTs/MFCs sheets	Proposed Concept
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Placed at selective places, hence min. number of units used. 2. Structurally attached, hence effectively sense vibrations. 3. Optimum places need to be determined by various optimization techniques. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do not skip any place of disturbance. 2. Effectively determine the characteristics of the generated vibrations. 3. Small disturbances can also be eliminated at any point. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Non-contact monitoring; 2. Making the structure light weight; 3. Entire region can be scanned, 4. The damping of any type of vibration is, no limit of max. possible values; 5. Highly durable in long run; 6. Can be fined tune at any frequency/ energy level so as to adjust to the vibrations of the membrane.

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